

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ABILITY IN STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL EDUCATION NEEDS

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Abstract. This article is dedicated to the development of creative abilities in students with special educational needs, and the ways to develop creative abilities in students with special educational needs, to increase their interest in creative activities, and to solve these problems are described in detail. .

Key words. Inclusive education, heuristic, abstract-deductive method, socialization, divergence, talent.

Introduction. The fundamental reforms being implemented in the socio-political, economic and cultural life of our country are as important for our society as updating the education system, which is one of the priorities of state policy, and educating the younger generation as a comprehensively developed person who can meet the requirements of the time, instilling in his mind the ideas of independence, setting tasks.

In order to strengthen the foundation of our independence and make Uzbekistan a great country, it is important to rationally implement educational activities, regularly acquaint young people with the achievements of modern science, culture, technology and technology. After all, the fate of development is decided by spiritually mature, strong-willed, full-faith, modern-thinking, high-potential individuals with certain professions. In this regard, in order to further improve the system of education for children with educational needs, the decision approved by PQ-4860 is of particular importance. In this decision, the decree "On measures to improve the system of education for children with special educational needs and to develop inclusive education" was announced.

In the following years, the study and analysis of the accumulated experience in the education system, including in specialized vocational schools for persons with disabilities, in the preparation of students with disabilities who need special support, in the development of their work and creative abilities. shows that in improving the content of study, work and vocational education, the physical or mental development of students and their interests are not taken into account, the education department in special schools, specialized vocational schools for persons with disabilities classification of teaching methods into scientific-theoretical, methodical and classroom activities, methods of teaching blind and visually impaired students, interactive methods in working with students with disabilities, creative due to insufficient application of these approaches, students with disabilities who need special support lack in-depth knowledge, skills and competencies about education and work values and professions.

Literature analysis. New literature is currently relevant for developing creative abilities of students with special educational needs, increasing their interest in creative activities, and solving these problems.

It should be noted that today, if educational technologies are not changed in teaching students with disabilities who need special support in special schools, then it is possible to imagine what kind of knowledge and skills they will have.

The problem of learning speech deficiency in children and its elimination was studied in the scientific works of L.R.Mo'minova, I.G.Veretennikova, Z.V.Babaeva, M.Yu.Ayupova, H.M.Polatova, N.Kh.Rakhmonkulova.

In the works of A.B. Abibullaeva, Yu.K.Babansky, E.A.Baydalinova, L.L.Burlyakova, V.P.Butkovsky, B.S.Gershunsky, V.A.Grachkov, students of general secondary education and vocational schools were employed in the countries of the Commonwealth of Nations. and vocational training were studied.

The problem of preparing students for work and profession in general secondary education and vocational schools in Uzbekistan A.Sh. Magdiev, T.J. Ismoilov, G.M. Muzaffarova, A.K. Nizomov, E.T. Ro'ziev, A.Yu. It was expressed in the researches of Teshaboev, S.B.Umarov, O'.D.Khidirov, P.N.Kholmatov.

If we look at the analysis of the scientific and pedagogical literature published in recent years at the level of our republic, the literature dedicated to the preparation of students with disabilities in special educational institutions for study, work and profession, and the development and creation of creative abilities in the lessons it can be seen that there is almost no research on Changes are taking place in the modern education system that affect all areas of the educational environment.

One of these changes is the introduction and strengthening of the practice of inclusive education, which implies the joint education and upbringing of disabled children, the presence of children with different educational needs in the educational process. Addressing the broad challenges of inclusive education requires new approaches that help develop the potential of every student.

The main part. Pupils acquire knowledge 40-60 percent faster and in a shorter period of time with the help of information and communication technologies than with conventional technologies.

Here we face the following problems in developing creative abilities and teaching students with disabilities.:

- lack of electronic textbooks and methodical manuals in Uzbek language on current pedagogical methods of developing creative abilities of students with special educational needs;
- Pedagogically and psychologically insufficient study of the personality of students in the development of creative abilities of students with special educational needs;
- programs taken from the former union are the basis of all links of the educational system of special schools, and not enough attention is paid to our national values and the formation of initial labor skills using them;
- absence of a creative approach based on the psychological and pedagogical characteristics of the development of creative abilities in students with special educational needs;

- lack of techniques in educational institutions for the development of creative abilities of students with special educational needs;
- insufficient creation of distance education systems for special schools and specialized vocational schools;
- lack of teaching manuals, methodical instructions on pedagogical diagnostic work on developing creative abilities of students with special educational needs;
- lack of creative approach by the teacher in the lessons;
- experience in the development of creative abilities of students with special educational needs is determined by the lack of special scientific research in our Republic.

Based on the study of research works on the problem and their scientific analysis, it became clear that the preparation of students of special schools for study, work and profession has not been thoroughly researched.

Literature on the teaching methodology for the development of creative activities of students on the preparation of students for study, work and profession in general secondary schools of our republic, and on the preparation of students for work and profession we can see that there is almost no research on creating e-learning resources.

Now the conditions in specialized educational institutions for persons with disabilities are changing radically. However, it is necessary to organize this activity, the processes leading to specific results, on a scientific basis. Currently, there is a need to connect students' vocational training with their interests.

In solving these problems, it is necessary to develop methods of creative ability development in students with special educational needs in educational institutions and take into account its pedagogical, psychological and methodical aspects suitable for students who need special support. Currently, some scientific articles related to the causes of diseases of students with disabilities, peculiarities in the development of students with disabilities, and the education provided to such students have been published. - methodical literature was published.

Inclusion is a process of increasing the level of participation of all citizens in society, primarily citizens with disabilities. The purpose of such education is to avoid social isolation of disabled children and deny them the opportunity to participate in the kindergarten community, school life, in other words, to ensure that all students receive education, taking into account the diversity of special educational needs and individual capabilities. is to ensure equal use. Currently, in Uzbekistan as well as in many countries, opportunities are being created for the education and training of children with disabilities, and the rights of such people and children are strengthened and protected by legislation.

Materials and methods. In the analysis of experimental tests on the development of creative abilities of students with special educational needs, we also took into account the youth who study at home, the main contingent of students in specialized vocational schools for disabled people of Fergana.

The following "Logical puzzle", "Who's smart" method, "Concept analysis" method, and "Find a pair" method were used as a pilot test in the vocational school.

Through the game "Who's the smartest", students have to find the names of trees and flowers with the letters in the given box. This serves to increase the wealth of the vocabulary, to form the qualities of inquisitiveness and resourcefulness.

The "analysis of concepts" method is used to determine the initial knowledge of the students, what concepts they have acquired, and what they have learned from today's topic at the end of the lesson.

"Find the pair" game. This game is one of the games that encourage creativity and can be used to reinforce a new topic, repetition and reinforcement lessons.

Results and conclusions. Through these game-based methods, we concluded that the world view of home-schooled students is more passive and that they need to be more individually engaged by each pedagogue. In all methods, the teacher-student tradition it has been proven to give good results. In general, the "Find a pair" method worked well.

Also, a chain game, a word game based on the field, a creative approach with the student, a mental wheel game, and memory exercises can have a good effect.

Children with disabilities are included in music, creativity, painting, visual arts, ceramics, physical education and sports, computer technology, sewing and other extracurricular clubs. At the same time, it is desirable to improve teaching methods in inclusive education and gradually introduce the principles of individualization into the educational process.

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